

Societal Impact of Culture in European Regions

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Abstract: The notion that culture plays a central role in development processes is increasingly accepted, both in academic circles and by public administrations and supranational institutions, with the European Union being particularly notable. From the realm of knowledge and research, there is a growing body of robust evidence establishing causal links between culture, creativity, and multiple impacts on social and economic variables. This paper synthesises the primary findings of a study that employs novel and intricate causal machine learning techniques to analyse the impacts of cultural and creative sectors on various dimensions of well-being in European regions, including income, employment, education, health, and sense of community, among others.

The results affirm that, in European OECD regions, the effects are positive across most dimensions for a majority of regions. This underscores the potential of culture and creativity to catalyse regional development processes and enhance the well-being of European citizens

Key words: Cultural and creative sectors, social impacts, well-being, regional development

Introduction. Where We Stand in the Evidence on the Role of Culture in Territorial Development.

The concept of culture's role in development is widely embraced by social actors and global organisations, evident from documents like the Ibero-American Cultural Charter, UNESCO Hangzhou Declaration, OECD papers on culture and local development, and European Commission records on cultural and creative industries. However, the global consensus lacks precision regarding causal links. Cultural experiences from the Cultural and Creative Sectors trigger transformative processes impacting economic and social variables, yet comprehensive theories and evaluation methods are underdeveloped.

The consensus underscores that vibrant cultural life reaps social and economic rewards in host territories, with culture's transformative effects touching individuals and collectives, fostering new relationships. This aligns with modern challenges like inequality, climate change, and technology's role, enhancing well-being, resilience, and identity. In Europe, the recent EU WORK PLAN FOR CULTURE underscores culture's fundamental role in democracies and individuals' lives, citing positive effects on well-being and social cohesion, along with fostering diversity and open dialogue in civil societies.

From a scientific standpoint, evidence has already solidified to establish a causal relationship between the dimension of cultural sectors in a territory and its per capita income or economic system productivity (Boix-Domènech, De-Miguel-Molina, & Rausell-Köster, 2022). However, these evidences do not unravel all transformational pathways, as the relationship between symbolic production, economy, and society is complex and multidimensional. We have only clarified some of these more evident relationships, such as the fact that the cultural density of a territory

attracts tourist flows (Cuccia, Guccio, & Rizzo, 2016; Plaza, González-Casimiro, Moral-Zuazo, & Waldron, 2015) or affects innovation through multiple mechanisms (Rausell-Köster et al., 2012).

Other studies confirm that cultural capital has a multiplier effect on human capital, generating greater impacts on growth processes and productivity enhancement (Sacco & Segre, 2009). Human talent needs to be connected to the territory – and only culture enables this – to apply its knowledge to the symbolic and material attributes of those geographic spaces, harnessing their potential.

In essence, there is already a theoretical framework and compelling evidence, although quite recent, that link the dimension of cultural and creative sectors with economic development dynamics across various territorial scales. The “state of knowledge” conveys that individuals’ cultural experiences and the corresponding projects, programs, and policies capable of supporting them act as catalysts, activating complex social processes that ultimately have effects on the overall well-being of citizens. These mechanisms extend far beyond the economic dimension.

The Relationships Between Culture and Well-being. Recent Contributions.

Thus, we are entering a new phase in which we realise that real processes of change are not solely materialised through economic impact but through social transformation. We are beginning to pay attention to the relationship between cultural and creative sectors and other social variables such as education (Mecocci & Bellandi, 2022) and, through cultural participation, to aspects like subjective well-being or health (Fancourt & Finn, 2019; Zbranca et al., 2022), civic engagement

(Campagna, Caperna, & Montalto, 2020), social cohesion (Otte, 2019), the environment (Burke, Ockwell, & Whitmarsh, 2018), or life satisfaction (Wheatley & Bickerton, 2019).

Hence, we are beginning to unravel the black box between culture, creativity, and variables that directly affect our well-being. It's important to remember that culture, as a producer of symbolic content, is an essential tool to transform our ideas and values, which can result in changes in attitudes and behaviours, crucial in the dual transition pursued by the European Union.

In this context, the study "Cultural and Creative Industries and the Well-being of Regions"¹ emerges. It is the first to address the effects of cultural and creative sectors (CCS) at a regional scale across a wide range of well-being dimensions, utilising some data modelling techniques originally developed with artificial intelligence and machine learning techniques.² In fact, the presented work is one of the most pioneering applications of these methods to study the regional impact of culture and creativity, also providing quantitative evidence to support its causal inferences.

Based on available data from 209 European regions, empirical evidence of the effects of culture and creativity

1 The presented doctoral thesis constitutes a recent contribution within the context of the European project H2022 MESOC. This thesis delves into the intricate relationship between cultural dynamics and regional development, building upon the foundation laid by the project's research objectives.

2 A database comprising 209 regions from European OECD countries, spanning the years 2008 to 2019, was utilised for the study. Employment data in the Cultural and Creative Sectors (CCS) were sourced from Labour Force Survey (Eurostat), and the list of sectors included within CCS followed the classification proposed by the "Measuring CCS in the EU" project (Vilares et al., 2022). The study incorporated the 11 dimensions of the OECD's regional Better Life Index.

on well-being is modelled and evaluated in two ways: first, in an aggregated manner, and then specifically for each region. The following well-being indicators, derived from the regional version of the OECD's Better Life Index (2018), are used:

Dimension	Indicator
Access to services	Households with broadband access (%)
Civic engagement	Voter turnout (%)
Community	People who believe they can rely on a friend in times of need (%)
Education	Educational attainment (%)
Environment	Particulate matter (PM2.5) in the air ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)
Health	Life expectancy (years)
Housing	Number of rooms per person
Income	Net disposable income per capita (Euros in purchasing power parity)
Employment	Employment rate (%)
Life satisfaction	Life satisfaction (0-10)
Safety	Homicide rate (per 100,000 inhabitants)

Source: OCDE (2018). Note: In health and employment, the most suitable indicator has been selected as there were more than one option.

The results corroborate that, for the majority of the considered socio-economic variables, cultural and creative activity has significant effects. It's important to note that the obtained results are not simple correlations; due to the techniques used (causal forest) and the causal models underlying them, they imply causality.

Hereafter, the joint effects of culture and creativity on well-being are presented. These effects should be interpreted as the increase an indicator of each dimension would experience in the following year (in its corresponding unit) in the event of a 1% increase in the proportion of employment in CCS. For instance, if a region's employment in CCS were to increase from 2% to

3%, its disposable income would rise by 348 euros (in terms of purchasing power parity, PPP) per capita for the entire population.

Source: Own elaboration.

Notes: Significance Codes: ' .1 '**' .05 '***' .01 '****' .001.

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Model quality is assessed based on model fit goodness measures. In the environment and safety dimensions, which use reverse indicators (reflecting pollution and homicides), signs have been reversed for straightforward interpretation.

Dimension	Effect	Signif.	Models quality
Access to services	0.386		Low
Civic engagement	0.024		Very low
Community	0.208	.	Low
Education	3.860	***	High
Environment	-0.193	**	Medium
Health	0.081	***	High
Housing	0.014	*	Low
Income	348.135	***	High
Employment	1.309	***	High
Life satisfaction	-0.001		Low
Safety	-0.001		Very low

Collectively, these results indicate that CCS have clear positive causal effects on education, health, income, and employment. They also impact housing and the sense of community, albeit with less statistical significance due to models not reaching the highest required standards of reliability. On the contrary, there is no clear evidence that CCS have statistically significant effects on access to services, civic engagement, safety, or life satisfaction.

However, these conclusions are challenging to generalise across all territories and times, given the heterogeneity characterising regions. This heterogeneity can lead to impacts of culture and creativity in one region being substantially different or even opposite to what is

observed in the aggregate. Consequently, an interactive web tool called SICCRE³ has been developed. This tool allows for specific estimations of the impacts of CCS on each region in an individualised manner. With SICCRE, tailored assessments of CCS impacts can be made for each region, taking into account their unique characteristics and context.⁴

Regional Distribution of Impacts

In assessing the effects of CCS on well-being, it's important to identify regions benefiting most. Due to constraints on the length, detailed analysis for each region isn't feasible. Instead, we'll outline general patterns where positive effects prevail. We'll count positive and negative impacts across dimensions, without assessing intensity or composition. For comprehensive regional insights, detailed analysis is advised, as effects can vary notably even among neighbouring areas.

Collectively, there are more positive effects than negative ones in the vast majority of regions (174 out of 209 regions). Nonetheless, it's noteworthy that only one region (Małopolska, Poland) experiences beneficial effects across all eleven dimensions. In other words, CCS isn't a one-size-fits-all solution and can generate adverse effects that differ in each context and should be monitored.

Six regions follow suit with positive effects on 10 out

3 <https://www.mesoc-project.eu/resources/SICCRE>

4 The regional results presented below may differ from those in the SICCRE platform since the latter are specific to the year 2019, while the averages of effects between 2009 and 2019 are presented here. Additionally, there might be some variations due to changes in the estimation methodology.

of 11 well-being dimensions: East of England, Espace Mittelland and Lake Geneva Region (Switzerland), Pomerania and Western Pomerania (Poland), and Western Greece.

Conversely, even in regions with a prevalence of negative effects, several dimensions still experience positive impacts. In these contexts, CCS can also contribute to certain aspects of well-being. Only 35 regions are in this situation, and among them, the majority (26) are on the border, with five dimensions having positive effects against six with negative effects. Regions with the least favourable outcomes include Drenthe (Netherlands) and the Lisbon metropolitan area, with only three dimensions having positive CCS effects (versus eight with negative effects). Following closely with four dimensions of positive effects versus seven negative ones are Berlin, Bremen, Luxembourg, Vienna, the Ionian Islands, North Aegean, Trøndelag (Norway), and Alentejo (Portugal). When including regions with five dimensions of positive effects, it becomes apparent that several are concentrated in the Netherlands and Norway.

The majority, on the other hand, falls in a medium to moderately high position concerning the number of dimensions with positive effects. Nearly 80% of regions (161 out of 209) have between six and nine dimensions where CCS generate positive effects.

Disparities between regions can stem from multiple causes. Firstly, differences in the internal composition of activities within CCS. Secondly, the structural characteristics of regions (economic, sociodemographic, political, etc.) that influence impacts and can intensify or moderate them. Lastly, and partly as a result of the previous two factors, the ways in which CCS interacts with its environment vary from one region to another.

Fig. 3. Number of Well-Being Dimensions (out of 11) with average Positive Effects Generated by CCS (2009-2019). Source: Own Elaboration

Considerations for Policy Makers and Cultural Ecosystem Agents

Global public policies have unmistakably elevated the importance of policies centred on the Cultural and Creative Sectors (CCS). This shift isn't confined to Western nations; emerging territories like Brazil and China have significantly reshaped cultural and creative landscapes within extensive development processes. In 2010, China's government designated cultural industries as a vital economic sector in its 12th five-year plan, offering substantial opportunities (Jianfei, 2011).

Cultural policies targeting cultural and creative sectors now hold central positions within public policies. This mandates greater responsibility, heightened intelligence, and more effective strategies for all participants in the cultural ecosystem—creative agents, cultural mediators, institutions, researchers, etc. Stereotypes and grand statements no longer suffice; the full array of resources, knowledge, and creativity must be harnessed, considering

the high opportunity cost.

As seen earlier, culture and creativity are emerging as versatile solutions to therapeutically address diverse social and economic challenges confronting the European Union, including “twin transitions.” The integration of culture and creativity as central, driving factors for European competitiveness is firmly established. This apex is represented by the diffuse European New Bauhaus project embedded in post-pandemic recovery efforts. In her late 2020 presentation, European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen proclaimed, “NextGenerationEU must launch a European renovation wave, making our Union a circular economy frontrunner. Yet, it transcends environment and economy; it’s a new cultural project for Europe.” Clearly, CCS possesses substantial potential to enrich quality of life across varied dimensions in European OECD regions. Thus, positioning them strategically in public policies, backed by specific plans due to significant economic and social profitability, is warranted. Well-aligned objectives and adept intervention tools render CCS interventions highly effective for regional development, yielding swift and enduring well-being benefits in education, health, income, and employment.

This perspective doesn’t overlook the core aim of cultural policies—to fulfil cultural rights. The strategic integration of symbolic resources in urban and territorial development derives legitimacy from citizens’ cultural rights, influencing their actual capacity to achieve dignified lives (Ramos Murphy, 2021).

Given their far-reaching impacts, interventions in culture and creativity are becoming the forefront of public policies aimed at societal transformation, particularly in Europe. This transformative endeavour requires reliable information, experimentation, intelligence, resources,

societal focus, stakeholder responsibility, determined political action, and civic participation. Ultimately, policies centred around culture and creativity must move from the periphery of public action to the rightful central stage, resolutely and responsibly.

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